

SMART 03

How to communicate by text with a smartphone

Different ways to communicate by text on a smartphone

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airelle

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SMART

MODULE 3

How to communicate by text with a smartphone

There are a number of different ways to communicate by text on a smartphone. This module will focus on a brief introduction to three approaches for sending textual information: **SMS messaging, e-mails** and **social media texting** through apps such as WhatsApp and similar applications.

What will you learn in this module

- 1 Understand the different ways that you can work with text messages on a smartphone
- 2 Receiving and sending text messaging using SMS
- 3 How to send and receive e-mails
- 4 How to send and receive social media text messages

Chapters in this module

1Introduction to messaging

2Sending, receiving and searching for SMS text messages

3Sending and receiving e-mails

4

Social network messaging to individuals and groups

Intended audience

The intended audience for this module are those who will help learners of all ages to become comfortable with using a smart phone to communicate.

Most of the content in this module is based on Android based smartphones. Other phones will have slightly different screens but the approach will be the same.

Important note: SMART Hands-on examples are through Android™

The content in this module is based around Android, a popular smartphone software in many regions.

You can send SMS messages, e-mails and social media texts on other non Android smartphones too such as an iPhone® and others.

While the images and approaches may change slightly for other smartphones, the basic ideas will be the same.

MODULE 3

CHAPTER 1

Introduction to messaging

Welcome to chapter 1 of the module SMART 03 “How to communicate by text with a smartphone”. It gives an overview with reference to the basic steps involved in messaging. Texting, also known as SMS or short messaging service, has been around for a long time now and allows you to send a short message to another smartphone.

What will you learn

- 1 Introduction to SMS messaging
- 2 Introduction to e-mail texting
- 3 Introduction to messaging through social media
- 4 Different styles appropriate for each type of messaging

Stay connected to the world!

We humans are social beings, social interaction is a natural aspect of life. Advances in technology have allowed easier communication across distances, cultures and time zones.

A quick response is very often required for urgent situations that arise in business, education and between friends. Modern smartphones feature most of the functions of the computer and texting is a rapid and convenient form of information exchange.

Three different styles of texting: which is the best one for you?

SMS messaging

This is the traditional way for people to send messages between smartphones. It is an alternative to making a call, and allows you to reach out to someone and allows them answer when they have time.

To keep messages short sometimes people use abbreviations; for more details on this look at Chapter 2 of this module.

E-mail texting

This approach originally started on computers but is also now available on most smartphones. E-mails are rarely formatted like an official letter, they don't generally contain formal phrases like *“Dear Sir/Madam”* or *“Yours Sincerely”*.

Emails are useful if you need to reach a friend or a family member who works on a computer without distracting their work routine. For more details look Chapter 3 of this module.

Texting with social media apps

WhatsApp and similar applications (apps) can be used with Wi-Fi giving a free text option without using mobile data if you are connected to a Wifi network. You may download these apps from Google Play™ (or App Store if you use an iPhone).

These apps allow you to reach others either individually or as a group.

Emoticons (emojis), short for “emotion icons” are very popular in group texting. For more details look at Chapter 4 of this module.

Texting: Pros and Cons

Advantages

- Convenient way to stay in touch with people
- Texts allow time for the recipient to respond compared to the need for an immediate response with a phone call
- Texts allow users to quickly respond to e.g. business or social gathering requests without unduly disrupting anyone's routine.

Disadvantages

- Texting can be addictive, leading to excessive use of a smartphone
- Texts are less personal than calls when you can hear the voice of the person
- Group social texts could be distracting to your lifestyle

Problem and Solution

The challenge

Smartphone navigation of icons and buttons can be challenging at first

Description of the solution

Practice makes perfect. Be brave! Touch an icon/button - see what happens.

Description of solution

Please try SMART module 1 for more information! Repetition also helps..

Result

Easier contact with friends and family is a great reward for time spent learning

Confidence comes with practice

Here are some challenges for you including topics that were covered in module 1. Throughout this module, we will be looking at practical steps for communicating by text. You should take opportunities to practice what you learn as you learn it. This will make it easier for you to remember. Some of these tasks are based on material from SMART 01.

- Try to connect your phone to an available network/ Wi-Fi
- Add your e-mail account, start communication
- Practice returning to the home screen on the smartphone
- To see more apps scroll right or left on the screen
- After a set period, think about your achievements using the smartphone. What can you do now that you didn't know how to do before?
- Ask your friends and family to text you to practice more!

 Did you know?

Emoticons or emojis are great forms of expression to add to conversations, making communication fun.

Quote

“ According to the philosophers Andy Clark and David Chalmers in a 1998 paper, our mental states, like our beliefs or our memories, aren’t always just in “in our heads”. They are spread out. In other words, it is not just that I use my contact list in my smartphone as a crutch to help me remember, my actual remembering is partly constituted by the phone itself. It is a combo of brain cells and computer chips.”

Michael Lynch, 2016, [theguardian.com](https://www.theguardian.com)

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 3** **CHAPTER 1** Introduction to messaging

Which of the following forms of communication can you do with a smartphone?

- Taking and sending photos
- Calls
- Messaging
- E-mails
- Morse code

Chapter summary

1

Introduction to text messaging (this chapter)

2

Using **SMS** or short messaging service, text is sent using mobile phone network (chapter 2)

3

With **E-mail** you can send a message to other computers and smartphones (chapter 3)

4

Social media texting allows you to send texts without a phone network (chapter 4)

5

Texting often uses abbreviations for common words or phrases such as u, btw, cu, 2moro

6

Texting sometimes involves the use of emoticons or emojis

7

Please progress on to the next module that focusses on SMS texting

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

Basic knowledge of texting options: SMS, e-mails, texts using social media apps

2

Understanding opportunities for better communication and social life using technology

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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SMART

MODULE 3

CHAPTER 2

Sending, receiving & searching for SMS text

In chapter 1 of this module we looked at an introduction to different ways of texting on the smartphone. This chapter will focus on the particular case of SMS texting. This is a common way of communicating by text between phones and predates the smartphone. SMS texting has been around since the 1990s.

What will you learn

- 1 How to send a new SMS message
- 2 How to reply to an SMS message
- 3 How to forward an SMS message
- 4 Adding acronyms and emojis into your messages

Introduction

Texting, also known as SMS or short messaging service, has been around for a long time now. Texting allows you to send a short message to another smartphone. This communication of the text happens across the mobile phone network, so SMS communication happens between two different phone numbers.

Important note: This chapter uses messaging using the Contacts list of a smartphone. Management of the Contact list is also covered in Module 2 Chapter 4.

TTYL

thx

XO

pls

GR8

LOL

cu l8r

rofl

TNX

 Did you know?

It is common practice to keep SMS messages short so sometimes people use abbreviations.

For example:

you in a text message could is often represented by the letter **u**

by the way could be **btw**

Friday could be **Fri**

January could be **Jan.**

See if you can figure out the meaning of these abbreviations.

brb

OMG!

GAL

vhg

Sending SMS texts

After making and taking phone calls, perhaps the next most common thing to do on a smartphone is to send a text message.

The first main topic in this chapter shows you how to do that.

How to communicate by text with a smartphone

1

Opening the text messaging app to send a text

Let's look now at the steps involved in sending a text.

To start sending a text tap with your finger on the icon for messages - this icon may look slightly different on different smartphones. Sometimes the word messages is written under the icon. As you can see on this picture the icon is blue. Sometimes it is orange.

You can enter the text messaging app by tapping on this icon.

2

3

How to communicate by text with a smartphone

1

2

3

Selecting the recipient

Once you have entered the text messaging app, the next task is to select the person that you want to send a text to.

To do this you click or tap on the place for adding the name and a list of possible names appears, populated from the contacts list on the phone. Then you can select a recipient by clicking or tapping on the contact name.

How to communicate by text with a smartphone

—

1

2

3

Entering a phone number of the message recipient

Alternatively if the details of the person you are texting are not already in the contacts list, you may wish to enter their phone number.

You can type in a phone number instead of selecting the name, by using the screen keyboard that pops up at the bottom of the window.

How to communicate by text with a smartphone

—

4

Adding a name to go with a new phone number

The text messaging app normally asks you to enter a name to associate with the number you entered, so the new number can be added to the contacts list.

5

Please just add in a name for the person.

6

How to communicate by text with a smartphone

Writing the message

Next you need to write the text of your message. To do that you first tap your finger at the place on the window where the text goes. This is shown as a grey box in the picture opposite. When you tap on this area the screen keyboard pops up at the bottom of the screen. You can then use this keyboard to type in your text message.

How to communicate by text with a smartphone

Sending the message

Once the details or number of the person you are texting is entered and the text message has been written, you simply tap on the send button or icon to send it. This is often a coloured button with an arrow on it as shown in the picture here.

Viewing and searching for texts

In addition to sending a text, you might also wish to view, search for or open text messages that have been sent to your smartphone. This next topic covers that task.

Please make sure to try this one out on your smartphone with texts that have arrived for you.

Viewing texts

1

How to know when a text has arrived

When a text arrives on your smartphone usually a shortened version of the message, showing the first few words, appears on your home screen.

2

3

4

Viewing texts

1

2

3

4

Viewing a text that has arrived

You can view the complete text of the message by tapping on this message and this opens up the messaging app.

Viewing texts

—

1

2

3

4

Opening a message that arrived previously to view it

While viewing the list of arrived messages, you can also tap on any one of the previously received messages to open the one that you want to view.

Viewing texts

—

1

2

3

4

Viewing a message that arrived previously

When you do this the details of the message will appear.

Searching for texts

1

Entering the messaging app to search for a text

When you wish to search for a previously received message, you tap on the message icon to open the messaging app as before

2

3

Searching for texts

1

2

3

How to search

You should see a list in chronological order of all the messages that have been received.

Now to look for a message, there's a search icon (magnifying glass) which you can use.

Tap on this icon to open the search tool.

Searching for texts

1

2

3

Typing in the name or a word you wish to search for

Now you type in the name of a person or a word that you are looking for.

The app will then search in all your messages for occurrences of that name or that word and you can find your message in that way.

Forwarding SMS texts

Once you have found and read a text, you may wish to **forward** it on to someone else.

Forwarding is where you send a message you have received on to one or more others.

Forwarding SMS texts

1

Selecting the message to forward

To forward a text that you've received, assuming that you've already opened the messaging app, you simply tap on the name of the contact whose text you wish to forward.

2

3

Forwarding SMS texts

1

2

3

Selecting the text that you wish to forward

You will see all of the recent texts between you and that sender.

Forwarding SMS texts

—

1

2

3

Choosing to forward a text message

Now instead of tapping, you need to press **and** hold the message that you wish to forward to another person.

This can take a bit of practice to get right!

Forwarding SMS texts

Selecting recipient of text

A menu will appear listing a number of options. Select the **Forward** option. Another window will appear populated with the names in your contact list. To send this message to another person you then select their name from the list. In this example it is a recipient called Jack Doyle.

Forwarding SMS texts

Sending the forwarded message

Jack Doyle has now been selected as the recipient, now it is time to send.

Tap the green arrow button in the corner of the app to send the message on to Jack Doyle.

Attaching photos and other files

You may also **attach** a photograph, document or other item to a text message. When you don't have a Wi-Fi connection, and you attach a multimedia file to a message, it becomes a multimedia message (MMS). Depending on the arrangement that you have with your broadband supplier, sending an MMS may be expensive.

Social media messaging is generally more popular for this. It is less expensive and more convenient. This approach will be covered in chapter 4.

Attaching pictures and other files

1

Selecting the message to forward

You can add an attachment after you enter the text of the message.

2

You do this in a couple of ways, by for example tapping the + sign to the left of the text message in the screen for a particular recipient.

3

Attaching pictures and other files

1

2

3

Choosing the type of attachment

When you do this, a number of options pop up at the bottom of the screen including pictures, photos and contacts (for sending one of your contact's details to another person).

In this case we will choose to attach an existing image by tapping **Pictures**.

Attaching pictures and other files

1

2

3

Selecting the file that you wish to attach

The next step is to choose the file (in this case an existing picture) that you wish to send by tapping on it.

Attaching pictures and other files

File is attached, now send

Once you tap the picture that you wish to send it will get attached to the message. A small version of the file should appear alongside any text that you have entered in the message.

Now you can tap the “Send” button to send the multimedia message.

Pros and cons of messaging

Advantages

- Convenient approach to stay in touch with a wide group of people as most people use texting.
- Texts allow time for the recipient to respond compared to the immediate reaction that is required with a voice call.

Disadvantages

- It could lead to excessive usage of the smartphone. You may need to watch the cost of texting!
- Texts are less personal than calls when you hear the voice of the person
- Group social texts could be distracting to your real-life routine

Quiz

Click the Quiz button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 3** CHAPTER 2 Sending, receiving and searching for SMS text

When you forward a text using the SMS app - do you have to press and hold on the message to forward it?

True

False

Process

The diagram illustrates the process of forwarding an SMS message. It shows a smartphone screen displaying a text conversation with 'Maria Silva'. A hand is shown pressing and holding a message, which is highlighted with a red box and the number '1'. A vertical arrow points down to a second red box with the number '2', indicating the next step in the process. The background of the diagram is a light gray gradient.

Chapter summary

- 1 Sending a new text message
- 2 Replying to a text message
- 3 Forwarding a text message
- 4 Acronyms and how to add them to your text messages

- 5 Text messaging is great for linking up with friends and family
- 6 This feature of a phone helps people to stay in touch or to arrange appointments
- 7 Practice with the examples shown here will improve confidence with smartphone

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

In this chapter you have learned how to send new SMS texts and how to reply to one.

2

You learned the style of short texting and hopefully you enjoyed playing with emojis!

3

You improved your smartphone navigation skills and hopefully added contact details to your list of contacts.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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SMART

MODULE 3

CHAPTER 3

Sending and receiving e-mails

This chapter provides guidance for how to send and receive e-mails. E-mail is another option to send text using a smartphone to someone. E-mails can be sent directly from your smartphone to someone's computer or smartphone. They can be sent using Wi-Fi which does not require using your mobile data.

What will you learn

- 1 How to send a new e-mail
- 2 How to receive and reply to an e-mail
- 3 How to forward an e-mail
- 4 The difference between official e-mails and e-mails to a friend

Introduction

E-mailing using a smartphone is an alternative to SMS texting. One big advantage of e-mail is that you don't need a phone signal and phone credit to get it working... you just need access to Wi-Fi.

The examples in this chapter use Gmail from Google – this is typically found on Android based smartphone. There are other e-mail apps (such as Microsoft® Outlook® and Apple® Mail) but the principles will be very similar.

Sending and receiving e-mails

It is very useful to be able to send and receive messages between smartphones and computers. This is an advantage of e-mails over text messaging and allows you to send messages to someone who is working at a computer.

E-mails can be answered without disruption of routine.

It allows smartphone users to communicate in a convenient way with family, friends and workers who are sitting at computers – causing less disturbance to their daily routines.

This chapter will look at how you use this useful communication feature.

The official style used in traditional letter writing that uses formal phrases like *“Dear Sir/Madam”* or *“Yours Sincerely”* is generally only used in e-mails when writing to or receiving information from Institutions.

Usually, the style used in e-mails is shorter and more informal, especially if you are e-mailing a friend or a family member.

Finding the e-mail app!

As we described in module 1, it can sometimes be a bit of a challenge to find the mail app at first. Sometimes the mail app is directly visible on the home screen, but sometimes it is partially hidden inside a folder on the home screen.

Tap the folder on the home screen with icons for search, browser, mail, Maps, etc.

The e-mail icon is generally an envelope or @ icon. Touch it to add your e-mail account or access your e-mails.

Receiving and opening an e-mail

This first topic looks at steps involved in receiving and opening e-mails.

Receiving and opening an e-mail

1

Opening the e-mail app

In order to enter into the mail system on your phone you need to tap on the icon for e-mail. As mentioned this is normally an icon with an envelope or @ sign on it but can be “hidden” in a folder on the home screen.

2

Next tap on the mail app icon.

3

Receiving and opening an e-mail

1

2

3

The main screen of the e-mail app – opening an e-mail

This opens up the e-mail app and it will show you the list of your most recent e-mails.

If you wish to look at the most recent e-mail, you look at the very top the list and tap on that e-mail.

Receiving and opening an e-mail

—

1

2

3

You are now viewing an individual mail

The app will show you the details of the e-mail.

Did you know?

Usually e-mail addresses are in the following form:

abraham.lincoln@gmail.com

abraham.lincoln@yahoo.ie

Very often the e-mail app you use helps you to search for an e-mail address that you have previously saved.

When you start typing an e-mail address you will see a list of any e-mail addresses that match what you have typed and you can tap the name of the person you want.

Replying to e-mails you have received

This topic looks at replying to e-mails
that you have received.

Replying to an e-mail you have received

1

View an e-mail you wish to reply to

Replying to an e-mail is one of the easier things you can do. Usually, a message appears on your screen to say that a new e-mail has arrived for you.

2

To view the new e-mail, just tap on the e-mail icon.

3

Replying to e-mails you have received

1

2

3

Opening the recently-arrived mail

Once you have opened the e-mail app, as before, you can tap on the new e-mail message in the main e-mail app window to select and view its contents.

Replying to e-mails you have received

1

2

3

Selecting reply

The selected e-mail opens in a new window. You simply tap the reply button to reply to the e-mail.

Replying to e-mails you have received

Adding the text of the e-mail reply

Now a e-mail window opens up where the e-mail address of the person you are replying to is already entered (because you have already selected their e-mail to reply to).

All you need to do is type in the text of your reply e-mail.

Replying to e-mails you have received

Sending the reply e-mail

Then as usual you hit the send button to send the e-mail to the person.

Quote

*“E-mails are simple to use as **global** citizens can organize their daily correspondence, send and receive **electronic** messages as well as save them on computers. **E-mails** are rapid. They are delivered at once around the globe. No other form of written **communication** is as fast as an **e-mail**”*

Krystal, Volney

2014, Science and Technology, wsimap.com

Sending an e-mail

This topic describes how you can send an e-mail to a contact by using the contact list or by typing in a phone number.

Sending an e-mail

1

Tap the e-mail icon to begin

To begin working with the e-mail app, you find the e-mail app icon on your home screen or a folder as outlined in previous slides.

2

This will open the e-mail app.

3

Sending an e-mail

1

2

3

The parts of an e-mail in the e-mail app

You usually need to enter three pieces of information to send an e-mail - the **recipient's e-mail address (To)**, the **subject title (Subject)** for the e-mail and the **text of the e-mail message (Compose mail)**.

Each of these will be covered in turn in the next 2 slides.

You will see that the **from:** box is already filled in with your mail address.

Sending an e-mail

1

2

3

Typing or selecting the name of a contact

Tap the **to** box and use the keypad at the bottom of screen to begin typing an e-mail address. The app will suggest e-mail addresses from your contact list that match what you type.

If you would like an explanation of contact management, it is in module 2 of chapter 4.

Sending an e-mail

Type the subject and compose e-mail parts of mail

Now you can type in the **subject** of the mail. This is optional, but it helps by giving the person you are sending the e-mail to an idea of what the mail is about before they open it.

Then type in the text of the mail in the **compose** part of the screen. This is the main detailed information that you wish to send.

Sending an e-mail

Don't forget to touch the Send button!

Now you simply tap the send button to send the e-mail.

Challenge: Three ways into an e-mail conversation: try using them on your smartphone!

Compose

Touch Compose, and it opens the keypad to allow you to type the e-mail address of your recipient and the text of your e-mail message.

Search in e-mails

If you are looking for specific piece of text within an e-mail or a person you have sent/received e-mails to/from, use this option and type the text or a name.

Open mailbox- reply, forward

This shows your recent e-mails. Select one of the e-mails and touch Reply. A keypad is displayed allowing you to type your text.

Did you know?

Who sent the first e-mail? Ray Tomlinson was the first person to send out an e-mail in late 1971. The electronic mail was sent between two machines that were side-by-side and the only physical joining they had was through the ARPANet, a precursor to what we now call the internet.

Email: Pros and Cons

Advantages

- Email is widely used. You can e-mail anyone in the world who also has an e-mail address
- You can deliver your information without disturbing the person with a call
- E-mail history can be used to keep a record of your communications
- With Wi-Fi access you get free e-mail communication compared to SMS texts

Disadvantages

- Be aware that texts and e-mails can become addictive and may take up a lot of your time!
- There is a need to keep a balance between virtual and communication in person
- You need Wi-Fi or mobile data to send an e-mail

More practice challenges

Here are some more challenges to reinforce what you have learned in this chapter so far.

- Practice texting using a social media network. See that it is similar to SMS texts
- Practice finding icons, buttons and discover some of their functions
- Ask friends or family members to text you! Reply to them!
- Follow the step by step guidance in this chapter and learn how to navigate WhatsApp on your smartphone
- Repetition helps recall!
- There are often two or more different ways to solve the problem, try one way then try another. See which you prefer.
- Remember your starting point and how far you have come in learning, recognise your achievements!

Problem and Solution

Indicate the task

Learning about Smartphone navigation using icons and buttons.

Describe the solution

Practice makes perfect. Touch an icon/button- see what happens.

Describe the solution

Repetition will improve recall.

Result

Easier communication with friends and family is a great reward for time and effort!

Some more challenges: sending and receiving e-mails

How to reinforce what you have learnt in this chapter.

- Become familiar with buttons, icons and their functions
- Follow the step-by-step process in this chapter
- Understand the main principles - touch an icon, it opens a box where you type your message and the keypad appears for you to use
- Practice! Engage with friends and family, ask them to send you e-mails and reply to them
- Go back and repeat the process
- Being up-to-date with technology will open a world of rich and interesting communications
- Teach your friends. It is the best way to remember!

Other functions related to e-mail

Finally, here are a few other functions that you may find useful and wish to try:

- Attaching files to an e-mail
- Deleting an e-mail

Other functions related to e-mail

1**2**

Attach files, photos

While you are editing an e-mail, touch the paperclip icon on the top of the screen. It gives you some options: Attach file or Insert from Google Drive™. If you touch the Attach button it opens access to your photos or files. Some people store their files in Google Drive.

Other functions related to e-mail

1

2

Deleting e-mails

You may sometimes wish to delete e-mails.

For this you can open the e-mail that you wish to delete and then use the Bin button on the top of the screen.

Challenge: Practice adding attachments and deleting mails

Attach a picture to a mail

Touch, compose, and create a mail for your friend, then use the paperclip icon to attach a picture to the e-mail.

Delete an e-mail

Open the e-mail app and find an e-mail that you don't need. Open the e-mail and use the bin icon to delete it.

✔ Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 3** **CHAPTER 3** Sending and receiving e-mails

Is the icon shown in the image the correct icon for an e-mail app?

True

False

Chapter summary

1

Sending a new e-mail

2

Replying to an e-mail

3

Forwarding an e-mail

4

The difference between official and social e-mails.

5

E-mail allows you send a message from your phone to a computer user

6

You can e-mail pictures or files from your phone using attachments

7

E-mail is a useful feature for business too.

8

If you use public Wi-Fi, an e-mail message is free.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

In this chapter you have learned how to open a new e-mail, how to reply to and send e-mails.

2

You have learned how to open a different folder on your smartphone to open the mail app

3

You have also learned about attaching files to your e-mail and deleting e-mails!

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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SMART

MODULE 3

CHAPTER 4

Social network messaging to individuals and groups

The final chapter in this module provides guidance for texting using Social Media apps. As mentioned in Chapter 1 of this module, a key advantage of social media texting is that it can be used for free with Wi-Fi. Another key advantage is that you can send text messages easily to groups as well as to individuals.

What will you learn

- 1 Messaging through social media: particularly WhatsApp, a popular app that could be installed on computers also.
- 2 How to share your message to a group to (for instance) organise a meeting or a social engagement.
- 3 Sharing pictures, photos or other files with your contacts.

Where to find social media apps

Go to Google Play store.

Example: download WhatsApp

Once you enter the Google Play store...

- in the search box enter the name of the app you wish to install, e.g. type WhatsApp
- tap Install and follow the steps to install the app

Did you know?

Other popular social media apps include:

- Messenger Facebook
- Snapchat
- Viber
- Skype
- Telegram
- KiK
- WeChat
- Line

Opening WhatsApp to view messages

To begin, let's look at how you open WhatsApp to view messages.

Opening WhatsApp to view messages

1

WhatsApp

We focus again on WhatsApp as a popular example of a social media app. It is an app that is generally used on phones, but more recently can be installed on a computer. WhatsApp has a very distinctive logo - a green logo with a phone in a speech bubble as shown in the picture opposite.

2

3

Opening WhatsApp to view messages

1

2

3

Opening WhatsApp

To open WhatsApp, you tap on the green WhatsApp icon on the home screen.

Opening WhatsApp to view messages

1

2

3

The main screen of WhatsApp

Very similar to opening up messaging and e-mail apps, what you see is the list of the most recent communications chronologically ordered.

Opening WhatsApp to view messages

Selecting message from a group or individual

While still in the main screen of WhatsApp, if you tap on a person's or group's name [go to step 5]

Opening WhatsApp to view messages

Viewing all of the messages from a selected sender

...you will see all the messages that you have exchanged with the contact with the most recent message at the bottom of the screen.

Replying to messages in WhatsApp

Next, we consider how to reply to messages in WhatsApp.

Replying to messages in WhatsApp

1

Replying to a message

It is really easy to reply to a message in WhatsApp. You just type your message in the little text box at the bottom of the window that appears after you have selected the message you wish to reply to.

2

3

Replying to messages in WhatsApp

1

2

3

Tap the send button

...and then simply tap on the little green arrow that appears alongside the text to send the message.

Replying to messages in WhatsApp

1

2

3

Returning to the home screen

When you have finished, to get back to the main screen then you just hit the left little arrow button at the bottom of your screen to bring you back to the main screen.

Sending a voice message in WhatsApp

Texting and voice calls are not the only way to communicate using WhatsApp.

Another interesting feature of WhatsApp, that is not a core feature of either SMS messaging or e-mail, is voice messaging.

This is where, rather than making a voice call, you send a voice recording so the recipient can listen to it when they have time free.

Sending a voice message in WhatsApp

1

Recording a voice message

Select the individual or group you wish to send the voice message to. A window opens showing your most recent messages to this contact.

2

In the bottom right-hand corner of the text window in WhatsApp is a little green circle with a microphone on it. If you tap and hold on it you can record a short voice message for this contact. When you release the microphone a voice message will be sent to the recipient.

Sending a voice message in WhatsApp

—

1

2

Beware the hazards of voice recording!

It is important not to tap that icon if you don't wish to send a recording of yourself to a group!

Adding an attachment to a message

It is useful sometimes to send photos, short videos and other files using WhatsApp.

Adding an attachment to a message

1

Adding an attachment

From the main message screen with a message selected, in order to add an attachment to a message tap on the paperclip icon.

2

3

Adding an attachment to a message

—

1

2

3

Selecting the attachment

Then you can select a file that you wish to attach. This could be an image, a photo, a location, a video or other items.

In this screen we are selecting the image of the tennis ball.

Adding an attachment to a message

1

2

3

Send message with attachment

To send the message with the attachment simply tap on the green arrow icon.

Quote

“Why do social messaging apps matter? Apps are taking over as the most popular way to connect with friends, family, and businesses. Many of these apps are free to use. Users can make voice calls, video calls, and send chats to others. It’s become an easy and cost-effective way for people to communicate, especially in countries where there aren’t unlimited text message plans.” (webbx.com)

Forwarding a message in WhatsApp

Just like with SMS messages and e-mails, you can forward messages in WhatsApp.

Forwarding a message in WhatsApp

1

To begin forwarding a message

To forward a message that you have received to another person or group, first you should be viewing the screen of messages from the person or group you wish to forward **from**.

2

3

Forwarding a message in WhatsApp

1

2

3

Opening the menu to select forward

PRESS and hold (rather than tap) the message that you wish to forward.

A menu pops up.

Forwarding a message in WhatsApp

1

2

3

Select forward

Tap on the “forward” option on the menu.

Forwarding a message in WhatsApp

Selecting the contact details of the recipient

Now select the person or group you wish to send the message to.

Forwarding a message in WhatsApp

4

5

Send the message

Now tap the send icon. The message is sent.

More challenges: Try out WhatsApp features!

Individual message

WhatsApp messaging is similar to SMS messages, described in Chapter 2 of this module.

Tap the message icon to send a new message to a recipient.

Reply to a message by typing text in the open panel. Don't forget to tap the Send button!

Create a group, then send a group message,

When you tap the WhatsApp icon, it opens a list of your messages.

There is an option called "New Group". Tap this and it opens your Contact List from which you select whom you want to add to the group.

Please also try group messaging; it is very useful for organising family chat groups, a hobby or exercise group (see HEALTHY modules). Or for keeping in contact with groups of co-workers or clients.

Sharing pictures

Sending photos by MMS message is expensive. A photo can be sent for free using a social media app if you are on Wi-Fi.

To try this, tap the Sharing symbol, it opens your other apps including photos.

Select and hold to select the photo you want to send. Choose how to send the photo - e.g. by e-mail or WhatsApp.

Social Media Messaging: Pros and Cons

Advantages

- Messaging with social media apps is free if you are using Wi-Fi
- Share your information with a group for faster communication
- Stay in touch with your friends, family or business partners!
- Share your pictures without additional costs

Disadvantages

- The constant arrival of group messages can be annoying. (you can mute messages for a day/week.)
- Social media can be used to facilitate the spread of upsetting or malicious fake news. Use only trusted message sources!
- Make sure that by engaging with other people's lives, you don't lose focus on your own activities.

Problem and Solution: adding a voice message...

Record voice message

When you open a message there is a panel with options: take a photo, go to your photo library and microphone symbol.

Challenge: Practice with WhatsApp

Indicate the task

WhatsApp navigation of icons and buttons

Describe the solution

Practice makes perfect. Touch an icon/button in the app - see what happens.

Describe the solution

Repetition improves recall. Please try out WhatsApp with friends and family.

Result

Easy communication with friends and family is a great reward for your time and effort!

Features of WhatsApp for you to try

WhatsApp often has a couple of ways to do different tasks.

Please try some of the following to reinforce your learning in this chapter.

Features of WhatsApp for you to try

1

Find Google Play Store which will lead to your apps

If you haven't tried it yet, Tap the Google Play Store icon shown in the picture and use the search box to search for WhatsApp.

2

WhatsApp should appear.

3

Features of WhatsApp for you to try

1

2

3

Install WhatsApp

Tap Install for the WhatsApp app in Google Play Store.

Features of WhatsApp for you to try

1

2

3

Try writing a new message

Once it is installed tap on the WhatsApp icon on your home screen to open the app.

To write a new message, tap the green symbol shown in the picture.

This opens a panel for entering text and a keypad for typing. Start typing the name of your intended recipient in the Recipient box - this displays any the contacts in your Contacts list whose name matches what you have typed. Select the one you wish to send the message to.

Features of WhatsApp for you to try

4

Try sending a group message

Tap the WhatsApp icon.

It opens your recent messages.

Select a group and type the message you wish to send to the group.

5

6

Features of WhatsApp for you to try

Try sharing a picture

Tap the Sharing symbol.

This opens your other apps including photos. Select **and** hold to tick the photo you want to send.

Chose how to send the photo - either by e-mail or WhatsApp.

Features of WhatsApp for you to try

Try sharing a picture: a second approach

When you have the panel open to type your message, tap the photo Gallery icon. Your pictures will appear, select one picture. Then tap Send!

✔ Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 3** **CHAPTER 4** Social network messaging to individuals and groups

Text messages can be sent using a social media app. You can find social media apps to install under Play Store folder.

True

False

The image shows a hand pointing at the Play Store app icon on a smartphone home screen. The screen displays the time 14:05, the date 19 February, and a search bar. The Play Store icon is highlighted by the hand.

Chapter summary

1

Social media apps such as WhatsApp can be used to send messages for free when using public Wi-Fi

2

You can share messages to a group to organise meetings or social engagements

3

Social media apps are also used for sharing photos or other files with contacts

4

Social networks help you to stay in touch with a group, club or family

5

You may need to download an App such as WhatsApp to do this

6

Practice with the steps shown in this chapter will help confidence with social media

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

Social network messaging to individuals and groups using the example of WhatsApp

2

Sharing pictures with others

3

Using social media to organise a meeting by sharing your message with a group

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

Module summary

1

There are three main types of text communication on a smartphone

2

These are SMS, e-mail and social network texting

3

SMS allows you to send and receive messages so long as you have a phone connection

4

E-mail can be used over public Wi-Fi for free and allows you to send mails to computers

5

Texting using social media text apps such as WhatsApp allows you to text a group

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1 You have learnt about SMS messaging

- 2 You have also found out about messaging using e-mails

- 3 You have learnt about social network messaging to both individuals and to groups

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this module or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)